

Geolocation of photovoltaic farms using Geographic Information Systems (GIS) with Multiple-criteria decision-making (MCDM) methods: Case of the Ecuadorian energy regulation.

ABSTRACT

Human needs and their production processes require energy services to be developed. In recent years, there has been a great interest in counteracting the use of fossil fuels to satisfy these needs. As part of the worldwide proposed initiatives, there is the use of renewable resources. In Latin America, renewable energy represents a large share of electric energy generation sources.

In the case of the Ecuadorian energy regulation, it is necessary to generate at least 1 MW to be considered as a solar farm. Under this framework, Ecuador has a project for installing 91 photovoltaic power plants, fifteen of which will be solar farms and the rest solar power plants with relatively low generation capacity. Currently, in Ecuador, photovoltaic projects are randomly distributed in the territory which shows a lack of adequate criteria for their location. The first step to promote the use of solar sources is identifying the potential, which can be estimated with the use of spatial tools such as Geographic Information Systems (GIS) with Multiple-criteria decision-making (MCDM).

This research aims to locate appropriate sites for installing photovoltaic solar farms based on the Ecuadorian energy regulation and combining GIS with MCDM techniques. Thus, nine factors and four restrictions were used for the analysis. Factors were weighted using the Analytic Hierarchy Process method. Once weighted, seven MCDMs were applied to select sites with solar potential. Subsequently, an analysis of seven results was performed using the Pearson correlation coefficient, followed by the absolute error analysis. By the coefficient of Pearson, it is demonstrated that there are methods with a high correlation between them. It is explained by the fact that they have many pixels with similar values, but these values are independent of geographical location. Regarding the results, Loja and part of the provinces in the center north of the country, Pichincha, Santo Domingo de los Tsáchilas, and Cotopaxi are the most adequate because of its great global solar radiation, wind speed, and temperature to cold the solar panels.

Keywords: Geographic Information Systems (GIS); Geolocation, Solar Farms; Multiple Criteria Decision Making (MCDM); Multicriteria Evaluation (MCE).

1. INTRODUCTION

Global climate change is caused by anthropogenic factors. To illustrate, some of them have increased since the pre-industrial era, such as economic growth, demographic density, fossil fuel dependence, modern large-scale agriculture, and land-use alteration. According to reports of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, energy demand and related services, focused on social welfare and economic development, are constantly increasing [1].

Renewable energies have a great potential to mitigate global change, and they can offer other profits if they are used correctly. Indeed, renewable energies can contribute to social and economic development, reliable energy supply, reduction of greenhouse effects, and better health status of populations [2]. The fast growth of renewable energies, specifically in the power sector, is due to different factors such as enhanced economic feasibility of these technologies, current policy initiatives, better funding, energy security, environment care, among others. In 2014, renewable energies produced around 19.2% of the world's energy consumption. Thus, new schemes for renewable energies in electricity markets have arisen in emerging countries. Statistics show that wind and solar energy reached record values during the last years, 77% of which are from new plants and the rest from hydroelectric power [3].

Currently, there is a global trend to generate more electricity from renewable energies per year than the power capacity of fossil fuels. Besides, the capacity of renewable energies is enough to satisfy around 24% of world power consumption, considering that 17% comes from hydroelectric power [3]. In this context, photovoltaic solar energy is one of the fastest-growing technologies in the world because of its competitiveness in financial terms compared to other renewable energies and fossil fuels [4]. During 2015 and early 2016, photovoltaic solar energy was spurred largely by historic low installation costs and a great number of energy auctions in Latin America, the Middle East, India, and the north of Africa [3, 5-7].

Furthermore, solar energy is the most abundant resource which can be used in two different ways: direct (solar irradiation) and indirect (wind, biomass, hydroelectric, etc.). To illustrate, even if only 0.1% of the solar energy could be converted with a 10% of efficiency, the resulting energy would be four times higher than the world power capacity, approximately 5000 GW [8].

In South America, a detailed analysis of the evolution of renewable resources and its quantity has not been carried out yet. However, good Examples of the application of renewable energies this are Costa Rica, Paraguay and Uruguay, which now satisfies more than 90% of their electric power demands using hydro, wind, or a mix of both [9]. For example, in Ecuador, according to the National Energy Balance in 2016, hydroelectricity supposes 45.6% of electricity generation. In this respect, Ecuador is trying to join these countries with an almost sustainable electric grid thanks to the construction of eight hydro power plants that represent summing an installed capacity of 2.76 GWp and some power

plants with minor capacity of Non-Conventional Renewable Energy (NCRE) [9]. Despite the government has promoted the encouraged the expansion of renewable energy technologies in the country using various policies, through the issuance of various regulations that promote their participation [10-12], the share of NCRE power plants in the national energy balance was still below one percent in 2016.

On the other hand, the European Union and eight Latin American countries, including Ecuador, started the project called “Euro - solar” in 2006. In the Ecuadorian case, the main goal is to improve the living conditions of 91 communities by means of energy access from renewable energies [13-15]. These communities are in Guayas, Morona Santiago, Pastaza, Orellana, Napo, Sucumbíos, and Esmeraldas. Additionally, the project wants to endorse the installation of solar power plants in isolated areas from distribution grids. In the same way, and thanks to private investment policies, several photovoltaic solar projects are under construction with rated powers around 1MW and 150 MW [10]. Now, Ecuador has 7 photovoltaic power plants connected to its interconnected power system, but none of them supplies electricity directly to nearby communities. Following the Regulation No. 002-14 of the National Electricity Council of Ecuador - CONELEC (09/01/2014), it is necessary to generate at least 1 MW to be considered as a solar farm. Under this framework, Ecuador has a project for installing 91 photovoltaic power plants, fifteen of which will be solar farms and the rest solar power plants with relatively low generation capacity [11].

1.1. Geographical Information Systems (GIS)

For this purpose, geographical information systems (GIS) have proved to be an indicated tool. GIS are designed to store, retrieve, manipulate, analyze, and plot geographic data [16]. Using GIS, interactive queries can be made to facilitate read information, spatial analysis, and user edition [17-18]. As a result of all these operations, maps are obtained. GIS handles their symbols according to a specific subject, and they consider cartographic rules that allow easy reading. Generally, maps are a decision-making tool within territorial planning studies, economic management, monitoring, and environmental care as well as a tool for selecting suitable sites for a specific activity [19]. The two-cover representation managed by GIS is based on raster and vectors [20]. The rasters (images) are represented through a grid of rectangles called pixels, which have the same size (resolution), specific information, and a geographical location. On the other hand, the vectors maintain a geometric figure (points, lines, and polygons) that is used to define limits associated with a reference system or a specific location in space [19].

The raster processes are faster for problems evaluation, including mathematical combinations such as the MCDM methods. GIS-MCDM methods environment is based on criteria represented by a layer of georeferenced cartographic information. Furthermore, every point of the territory received a value regarding the object activity of the decision [19].

GIS-MCDM methods have proved to be a useful tool for regional renewable energy potential estimation [21-23] and effective support for decision-making in energy planning [23-26]. Recently, many researchers have used GIS-MCDM methods to select a suitable place for solar energy-based plants [26-29]. Particularly, Beccali et al. used the ELECTRE III technique to evaluate the active program for the development of solar energy [26]. Carrion et al. presented an environmental decision support system to select suitable site of grid-connected PV power plants. MCA and AHP were used to select suitable sites in the GIS environment. In this study, Environmental, Geology, proximity, accessibility, and climate criteria are used to select the suitable PV sites [27]. Uyan integrated the MCA and AHP to find a good location in Turkey. As a result, 13.92% of the study area was in the very suitable class and 40.34% of the area was not suitable [28]. Sanchez-Lozano et al. developed a framework, which integrated GIS, AHP and TOPSIS models, to select the suitable PV sites. The weights of the different criteria were calculated by the AHP, and the ranking of the PV sites was obtained by applying the TOPSIS model [29].

1.2. Multiple Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) Methods

Solar farm sitting is an MCDM problem. The best location for solar farm settlement is based on considering electrical and communication infrastructures as well as environmental and economic feasibility. This shortcoming can be dealt with by adopting MCDM [30]. The selection is made by several alternative locations by a set of criteria and possibilities. MCDM methods are analytical tools employed to judge the best alternative of a set of possibilities and easy to adapt to different requirements. The evaluation of MCDM methods compares different elements according to their characteristic properties to select the best alternative for solar farm location (distance to urban areas, distance to distribution substations and transmission lines, land uses, distance to ports, airports or terminals transport, slope, wind speed, air density, etc.) [29-32]. The MCDM methods can be broadly divided into two categories; (i) multi-objective decision making (MODM), and (ii) multi-attribute decision making (MADM). There are also several methods in each of the above-mentioned categories. Priority-based, outranking, preferential ranking, distance-based and mixed methods, are some of the popular MCDM methods commonly used to select a location for renewable energies [32-35].

The application of MCDM methods has been conducted in many disciplines. For instance, Sindhy et al. [33] and Ho [35] performed several applications selection, which integrated the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP). Recently, there are many examples of the application of MCDM methods in renewable energy sources [36-40]. In particular, Saraswat, et al. [36] presented a GIS-MCDM based modelling technique for the assessment of solar and wind farm locations in India. Prieto-Amparán, et al. [37] developed a regional GIS-assisted multi-criteria evaluation of site-suitability for the development of solar farms. Wang et al. [38] combined Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) and Grey Based Multiple Criteria Decision Making (G-MCDM) for solar PV power plants site selection in Vietnam. Günen [39] presented a comprehensive framework

based on GIS-AHP for the installation of solar PV farms in Kahramanmaraş, Turkey. Deveci, et al [40] evaluate criteria for site selection of solar photovoltaic (PV) projects using fuzzy logarithmic additive estimation of weight coefficients.

1.3. GIS with MCDM methodology

The application of MCDM methods and GIS plays an important role in the pre-feasibility and feasibility analysis of renewable energy projects because it aims to conduct accurate management of budgets and natural resources. GIS-MCDM methods mix spatial information and criteria weights [24]. allows the identification of optimal locations for solar power plants, based on a weighted overlay analysis of satellite retrieved high-resolution data of solar energy resources and climate conditions, over-layered with the relevant topographical, land use, community settlements, and electrical network data layers [23]

There is previous research that applied MCDM methods and GIS techniques in renewable energy systems planning [41-44]. For instance, Saraswat, et al. developed GIS-MCDM based modelling technique for the assessment of solar and wind farm locations in India. [42] Díaz-Cuevas et al- performed A. Integrating GIS-MCDM for renewable energy spatial models for wind, solar and biomass energy in Southern Spain. Gwo-Hsiung et al. [43] studied the use of MCDM for the development of a new energy system in Taiwan by AHP and the Preference Ranking Organization Method for Enrichment of Evaluations (PROMETHEE). Also, the decision-makers (DSS) and PROMETHEE techniques were applied by Georgopoulou et al., [44] for new renewable energy exploitations. In the same approach, Pohekar and Ramachandran [45] published a review for a sustainable energy-planning project, which included MCDM methods such as PROMETHEE, AHP, Elimination, and Choice Expressing Reality (ELECTRE), Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS), Fuzzy, etc. More recently, Lee et al. [46] developed a model based on AHP associated with benefits, opportunities, costs, and risks (BOCR) for a strategic selection of wind farms in China. Sánchez Lozano et al. [23] carried out a multi-criteria evaluation for solar farms located in southeast Spain. San Cristobal [47] developed GIS-MCDM methods in the selection of a renewable energy project in Spain: the Vikor method. Besides, Watson and Hudson in [48] assessed the suitability of wind and solar farms (at a regional scale) using multiple criteria assisted by GIS and Multi-Criteria Decision Methods (MCDM) combination.

Likewise, particularly, in the selection of solar farms with GIS-MCDM methods have several studies [17, 18, 20-29, 31-33, 36-59] such as Janke in [49], which developed geolocated suitable places for wind and solar parks in Colorado as well as Tahri, Hakdaoui, and Maanan in [50] evaluated the location of solar farms in Morocco. In addition, Furthermore, 24% of the total area of Souss-Massa, southern Morocco, was established as suitable for solar farms by a GIS and MCDM evaluation method [51]. In the same way, the combination of these two methods was determined as reliable in [51-54]. To be specific, large photovoltaic farms in Brazil were suitable in 19.91% of the evaluated areas which are concentrated in the extreme south of country [54]. Additionally, the location of

large-scale photovoltaics and concentrated solar plants was successfully determined by these two methods in Ningxia, China [55]. A similar study was conducted in Mauritius where the northern area presented profitable characteristics for solar farms [56]. Furthermore, a Methodology for Ecotourism Site Selection in Black Sea Region of Turkey was developed in [57]. Finally, a review for Landfill Site Suitability Analysis was exposed in [58].

In case of Ecuador, Cevallos-Sierra and Ramos-Martín [9] developed a GIS study of the areas with higher potential for the accomplished renewable energy projects (REP). As a result of the study, the areas with higher potential for the development of REP have been identified and classified in spatial layers according to its technology and location. These results show that solar PV is the technology with most suitable areas in the country and demonstrate particularly large potential in two regions: the Andes cordillera and insular region, especially in the provinces of Loja, Pichincha and the Galapagos islands.

This research aimed to analyze the most feasible location for installing photovoltaic solar plants based on GIS-MCDM based on the Ecuadorian energy regulation, which will be explained as follows. In this research, the ArcGIS software is used to rasterize and standardize the data layers under linear and logistic functions. From this first step and with the inputs generated, the multi-criteria analysis and the comparison of results are performed using R, which is a programming language specialized in calculus and statistics. For this purpose, variables such as road network, temperature, wind speed, existing electrical transmission lines, urban areas, and their buffer zones, slopes, land use coverage, stations, and substations have been considered. The MCDM methods applied in this research are the AHP method, which needs the computation of the ARAS, Occupational Repetitive Actions (OCRA), PSI, SMART, Weighted Superposition, TOPSIS, and VIKOR. In the same way, an Overall Performance Index (OPI) is applied to evaluate the results. Finally, the mutual correspondence between MCDM methods is evaluated using a Pearson correlation coefficient. As seen in the literature review, the use of this methodology all together in the article is novel.

Finally, the paper is organized as follows: The Materials and methods for the study are described in Section 2. The results are presented in Section 3. The discussion of the results is described in Section 4, and the conclusions of the research are exposed in Section 5.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The methodology for obtaining the suitable geolocation of solar farms in Ecuador is based on decision-making processes applying comparison methods and criteria weighting techniques. Therefore, decisions are fully consistent with the reality of the area under study.

The procedure begins with the collection of spatial information. This information should be classified according to the case as factors or restrictions in order to define the necessary factors and restrictions. Next, this information is classified, and its characteristics are defined as scales and resolutions. Later, the information was transforming into a raster

format and it is already standardized. As part of these two processes, the geoprocessing tools of ArcGIS are used. Finally, MCDM is processed using the weighting criteria of the AHP method. Defined the weights, MCDM methods indicated in the theoretical framework were preceded. With these results, visual and statistical comparisons are made using the Pearson coefficient analysis and absolute error analysis. Through this analysis, the best result for the sectioning of sites is determined. Figure 1 depicts the proposed methodology. Here, the flow diagram is divided into three phases for a better explanation.

Figure 1: GIS and MCE processes

Before using MCDM methods, the used weighting factor needs to be considered. There are qualitative methods that allow studying the relationship between variables and developing an integral and holistic evaluation. They have the property of enriching and qualifying quantitative information. They can achieve the quantification goal if they are assigned a value to indicate a greater or lesser degree of the attribute in the object [8,10].

For this research, a combined complex qualitative method called the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) was taken into account, which allows assessing and weighting at once. Subsequent, MCDM methods are applied. This paper has applied seven different methods: Additive Ratio Assessment (ARAS), Operational Competitiveness Rating Analysis (OCRA), Preference Selection Index (PSI), Simple Multi-Attribute Rating Technique (SMART), Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS), Weighted Overlay, and VIKOR. Each methodology is detailed in the references cited in [17-59]. Down below, an explanation for the used GIS process and MCDM is provided.

2.1. GIS METHODOLOGY

GIS methodology includes the definition of geographic extent and information collection, information gathering, factor standardization, scale and resolution definition, rasterization information as well as standardization and homogenization of scales. Below, each section is detailed.

a) Definition of geographic extension and information collection

The Ecuadorian continental territory is divided into three natural regions (Coastal, Andean, and Amazonian). Each region has its own physical, environmental, and social characteristics. In this research, these three regions are analyzed. Although it is known that the Andean region presents higher global solar radiation due to the Andes Mountain Range, it is crucial to know the solar incidence in the entire continental part of Ecuador. Under this context, the proposed study aids to define suitable sites for installing photovoltaic solar farms that supply electricity to populations located far from the NIS and even eventually to the NIS. The mentioned three regions appear in Figure 2. The Andean region covers an area around 70 thousand square kilometers which is approximately one-third of the continental territory of Ecuador [60].

Figure 2. Location map of the study

b) Information gathering

Institutions involved in the energy sector and entities responsible for generating base cartographic information are well defined in Ecuador. For instance, the Ministry of Electricity and Renewable Energy (MEER in Spanish Ministerio de Electricidad y Energías Renovables), Electric Regulation and Control Agency (ARCONEL in Spanish Agencia de Regulación y Control de Electricidad), and the National Institute of Energy Efficiency and Renewable Energy (INER in Spanish Instituto Nacional de Eficiencia Energética y Energías renovables) conform and produce information regarding the energy sector. Meanwhile, different institutions generated the base cartographic information, such as the Military Geographic Institute (IGM in Spanish Instituto Geográfico Militar), Ministry of Transport and Public Works (MTOPE in Spanish Ministerio de Transporte y Obras Públicas), Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock, Aquaculture and Fisheries (MAGAP in Spanish Ministerio de Ganadería, Agricultura y Pesca), Ministry of the Environment (MAE in Spanish Ministerio del Ambiente), National Institute of Statistics and Censuses (INEC in Spanish Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Censo), and the National Institute of Hydrology and Meteorology (INAMHI in Spanish Instituto Nacional de Meteorología e Hidrología). The date of the data corresponds to the latest data submitted by the institutions in early 2021.

Table 1 details the collected information per institution, generation year, spatial scale, and coverage type. The selected coverages in table 1 are the most used in this type of studies according to the bibliography [61-64].

Table 1: Detailed the information collected by institution, generation year, spatial scale, and cover representation type.

Information coverage	Institution	Year	Scale	Cover representation type
Digital elevation model (DME)	MEER	2013	200 x 200 m	Raster
Wind Speed	MEER	2013	200 x 200 m	Raster
Annual average global radiation	ARCONEL	2008	1000 x 1000 m	Raster
Substations	ARCONEL	2015	50000	Vector
Transmission lines	ARCONEL	2015	50000	Vector
Average annual temperature	INER/INAMHI	2015	200 x 200 m	Raster
Road network	MTOP	2015	50 000	Vector
Vegetable cover and land use	MAGAP	2013	100 000	Vector
Urban areas	IGM	2013	50 000	Vector
Water areas	IGM	2013	50 000	Vector
The National system of protected areas	MAE	2015	250 000	Vector
Andean region limits	INEC	2013	250 000	Vector

c) Factors standardization

Factors are based on the weighting and compensation of variables. They will influence positively (aptitude) or negative (impact or unfit) on the activity or decision object that must be previously inventoried and classified [59]. Table 2 summarizes the selected information and each type of criteria considered for the evaluation:

Table 2: Factors and restrictions

Information coverage	Criteria
DME	Factor
Wind speed	Factor
Annual average global radiation	Factor
Substations	Factor
Transmission lines	Factor
Average annual temperature	Factor
Road network	Factor
Vegetable cover and land use	Factor
Urban areas	Factor/restriction
Water areas	Restriction
The national system of protected areas	Restriction
Ecuador continental limits	Restriction

d) Scale and resolution definition

Working with information in raster format is considered ideal in MCDM methods evaluation. For this reason, changing a vector coverage to raster is necessary to establish a known extension grid, whose precision is defined by cell size. In this study, the pixel resolution of collected rasters (wind speed, digital model of elevation, and temperature) is 200m x 200m.

f) Rasterization information

In this stage, format and resolution are defined and coverages are classified (in factors and restrictions). Previously, it is important to review the related bibliography to determine the rasterization processes and evaluation criteria [17-59]. Thus, the next research were considered: "Multi-criteria GIS modeling of wind and solar farms in Colorado" by [50], "PV site suitability analysis using GIS-based spatial fuzzy multi-criteria evaluation" by [62], "Geographical Information Systems (GIS), and Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM). On the other hand, the evaluation of solar farms locations was carried out following these references: "A study case in south-eastern Spain" by [42]; "GIS-based solar farms site selection using analytic hierarchy process (AHP) in Karapinar region, Konya / Turkey" by [28], "The evaluation of solar farm locations applying Geographic Information System and Multi-Criteria Decision-Making methods: Case study in southern Morocco" by [51], "Wind farms suitability location using geographical information system (GIS), based on multi-criteria decision making (MCDM) methods: The case of continental Ecuador" by [32]. Since these documents, Table 3 were built for rasterization processes:

Table 3: Rasterization processes by coverage

Information coverage	Rasterization process
DME	Slopes in%
Wind Speed	Rescaling the raster to 5 meters high
Annual average global radiation	Rescaled resolution to 200 x 200m
Substations	Euclidean distance
Transmission lines	Euclidean distance
Average annual temperature	Without rasterization processing
Road network	Euclidean distance
Vegetable cover and land use	Classification and rasterization of level II
Urban areas	Euclidean distance / binary Raster
Water areas	Binary Raster
The national system of protected areas (SNAP)	Binary Raster
Ecuador continental limits	Binary Raster

- **DME:** This raster lets to obtain slope coverage classification in degrees or percentages. DME was converted into a gradient raster classified in degrees (°). According to [32, 47], the slope should be less than 15° equivalent to 3% in order to the site will be optimal for photovoltaic farm installation. The lower the slope the greater the aptitude of the land for the construction.

- **Wind Speed:** This criterion is considered as a factor since at higher wind speeds the system can be better cooled [63]. Also, solar panel inclination should not exceed 15 ° in Ecuador because of its location in the central meridian and parallel. Therefore, the air gap between photovoltaic systems and the lower surface must be at least 20 cm for proper cooling. In addition, it should be considered that photovoltaic panels installed on roofs do not reach extreme temperatures [47]. This paper presents a calculation of vertical profile for wind, considering speeds for heights equal to 30, 50, and 80 meters. The process performed is observed in Figure 3.

- **Average annual temperature:** This factor is collected in raster format. The minimum and maximum values of global solar radiation are registered in Ecuador, respectively 3634 and 5748.47 Wh/m²/day per year, respectively. The process appeared in Figure 4.

- **Substations:** In this case, the proximity to substations has a key role to ensure a close coupling point and avoid losses in transmission grids [32]. Therefore, the process defined for rasterization is the Euclidean distance.

Figure 3: Flow chart to obtain the wind speed raster at the desired height

Figure 4: Flowchart to rescale the resolution of a raster

- **Transmission lines:** It is important that solar projects are located as close as possible to transmission lines to ensure connection to the central grid and minimize transmission losses. In other words, establishing a system of distributed generation [32]. Additionally, installation costs could decrease when distances between solar farms and

transmission infrastructures are short. Then, the utilized rasterization geoprocessing is the Euclidean distance.

- **Annual average temperature:** It ensures the proper operation of solar farms [32, 47]. The parameter most affected by the increment of temperature is voltage, and consequently the generated power and energy. The electrical efficiency of photovoltaic panels depends on ambient temperature, and it is reduced when temperature increases. Also, electrical efficiency varies from one type of solar technology to another. In 2015, the Dash study "Effect of temperature on the power output of different commercially available photovoltaic modules" concluded that the highest performance of photovoltaic panels is achieved in extremely low ambient temperatures. Also, it mentioned that the degradation rate of photovoltaic cells is only -1.5% yearly [64]. Other studies, such as "Temperature-dependent photovoltaic effects in the manganite-based heterojunction" by Sun et al. 2014. With the above clarifications, it is justified that this factor should not go through any rasterization process since its resolution 200 x 200 m, and its extension covers the desired area.

- **Road network:** can be categorized in the same group of substations and transmission lines because it is important that solar projects are closest to existing infrastructure. An accurate location for this type of projects is given by good accessibility, assessed by the distance to main roads [32]. In addition, this proximity contributes to having an idea of future building costs. As a result, this proximity avoids additional costs for construction of solar farm and environmental damage [62]. In this way, the applied rasterization geoprocessing is the Euclidean distance.

- **Vegetation cover and land use:** Soil suitability is classified according to the usage type and vegetation cover. The ideal location is in sterile areas of agricultural use and short vegetation, such as shrubs, meadows, pastures, bushes, steppes, and exploited areas that would not prevent wind or reduce solar insolation. While the unsuitable areas have vegetation with ecological importance and high amount of species, such as protective forests. Furthermore, unsuitable places can also contain rocky areas, glaciers, and urban areas [32, 47].

Two levels of detail or categories are used to analyze this coverage. Therefore, the rasterization process is also applied to convert polygons to raster. Moreover, the level code is applied as the rasterization field. It is shown in Table 4:

Table 4. Classification of vegetation cover and land usage according to level 2

Level I	Code I	Level II	Code II	Standardization
Forest	1	Native forest	11	15
		Forest plantation	12	15
Agricultural land	2	Annual cultivation	21	50
		Semi-Permanent Cultivation	22	50
		Permanent cultivation	23	50
		Other agricultural lands	24	80
		Pastureland	25	80
		Agricultural mosaic	26	60
Shrub and herbaceous vegetation	3	Shrub vegetation	31	100
		Moorland	32	90
		Herbaceous vegetation Natural	33	70
Water areas	4	Natural	41	0
		Artificial	42	0
Anthropic zone	5	Populated area	51	0
		Infrastructure	52	0
Other areas	6	Area without plant cover	61	10
		Glacier	62	0

- **Urban areas:** Solar farms located close to rural and urban residential areas can cause negative impacts on the environment and neighboring people related to land use and thermal pollution. Thus, a minimum distance of 500 meters should be kept between urban areas and solar farms [32, 47]. In this sense, a buffer zone of 2 km around urban areas is employed, considering environmental care and the future growth of human settlements. This process was carried out using the "area of influence" tool, which is available in GIS. Next, for the rasterization process, the Euclidean distance tool is used. The closest infrastructure of the buffer zones, more suitable the analyzed site will be. This concept makes easier solar farms connection to NIS or neighboring populations.

Down below, Figure 5 and Figure 6 show the rasterized factors considered for this analysis.

Figure 5: Rasterization factors I

Figure 6: Rasterization factors II

On the other hand, a 2-km buffer zone around urban areas is considered as a restriction. Also, this input data is rasterized to convert the buffer zone into a binary raster. That is, a raster made up of values between 0 and 1 in which suitable areas are represented by number 1, and the unfit zones are represented by 0 for each pixel. The same process is used with other three coverages considered as restrictions.

The rasterization process consisted of converting into a binary raster where water bodies and SNAP adopt zero value as unfit areas. According to the Environmental Legislation of Ecuador, these elements are considered as preserved zones which should not be intervened by human activities.

Next, the four built binary rasters are multiplied among them, using a raster calculator, to obtain a single restriction coverage. It will subtract unfit areas in the final site selection. Figure 7 shows the restrictions considered.

Figure 7: Rasterization restrictions

g) Standardization and homogenization of scales

The standardization process consists of rescaling values from an input raster, using the previous specified mathematical function, to predefined standardization criteria. Most of the coverages are standardized applying logistic decrease function (when lower values are preferred) and logistic growth (when higher values are preferred). These standardization functions are part of the available tools in ArcGIS geoprocessing software, in which coverage is uploaded and the rating scale is specified (from 0 to 100). The defined processes for each coverage are detailed in Table 5.

Table 5: Factor standardization processes

Coverage information	Standardization process
DME	Logistics decay function
Wind Speed	Logistics decay function
Annual average global radiation	Logistics decay function
Substations	Logistics decay function
Transmission lines	Logistics decay function
Average annual temperature	Logistics decay function
Road network	Logistics decay function
Vegetable cover and land use	Reclassification according to its importance
Urban areas	Logistics decay function

For plant cover factor and land usage, multi-criteria assessment, with a scale from 0 to 100, is used to qualify them according to level two detail. Reviewed bibliography suggests that areas depleted of vegetation or zones with short vegetation should receive the best valuation.

In this standardization stage, the hedges defined as restrictions are not considered because they alter results. Restrictions are useful to classify areas with greater or less aptitude for the purpose. The factor standardization is shown in Figures 8 and 9.

Figure 8: Factor standardization I

Figure 9: Factor standardization II

2.2 MULTI-CRITERIA DECISION METHODS (MCDM)

The MCDM methods applied in this research are the AHP method, which computes the ARAS, Occupational Repetitive Actions (OCRA), PSI, SMART, Weighted Superposition, TOPSIS, and VIKOR. An Overall Performance Index (OPI) is utilized to evaluate the results.

a) Criteria weighting

Defining the problem and actors, structuring the problem, performing a hierarchical model, entering the weights or judgments, and evaluating the consistency of results are the mandatory steps for the assignment of factors weight [32].

Weighting factors are determined by AHP hierarchical analytical process. At the beginning of the process, factors are structured by assigning membership groups and ordered according to their hierarchy, see Figure 10. Here, numerical values or weights for

each factor are defined. With this process, the variable with the highest priority for the analysis is observed.

The definition of numerical values or weights for each factor is based on the next bibliography list: "Multicriteria GIS modeling of wind and solar farms in Colorado" by [50], "PV site suitability analysis using GIS-based spatial fuzzy multi-criteria evaluation" by [62], "Geographical Information Systems (GIS) and MCDM methods for the evaluation of solar farms locations: Case study in south-eastern Spain" by [41], "GIS-based solar farms site selection using analytic hierarchy process (AHP) in Karapinar region, Konya / Turkey" by [28], "The evaluation of solar farm locations using Geographic Information System and MCDM: A Case study in southern Morocco" by [51], and "Wind farms suitability location using geographical information system (GIS), based on MCDM: The case of continental Ecuador" by [32]. Thereafter, the weighting must add up to 100% for any hierarchical group or analysis case. The proposed weighting is presented in figure 10.

Figure 10: Weighting Factor

Once the used factors in the study are weighted, they are grouped into three important components. This labeling responds to the hierarchy. The climatic group is the highest valuation over 40%, the socioeconomic group with 35%, and the environmental group with 25%. Afterward, MCDM methods are applied, and in this case, there are seven selected methods: ARAS, OCRA, PSI, SMART, TOPSIS, VIKOR, and weighted superposition. All these methods use the previously defined factors and weights. Each methodology is detailed in the cited references [17-59].

b) MCDM evaluation

Once the MCDM methods results are obtained. They are evaluated and compared to each other. Statistically, there are several techniques that allow comparing results. In this case,

raster coverages are compared (the result of the MCDM), recognizing visual and numerical similarities in the analyzed data sets at the present time.

Numerical comparisons employ procedures based on statistical and mathematical models to find relationships among large data sets. In this case, the Pearson correlation coefficient and a calculation of the error analysis is considered. Here, the correlation is the appropriate analysis method to know the possible relationship between two variables of this type [32, 63].

c) Pearson Coefficient

Equal to other research based on GIS techniques, this paper makes a comparison between a pair of maps using Pearson correlation coefficient [32, 65]. Pearson correlation coefficient measures the degree of linear association between two variables which is computed by dividing the covariance of both variables by the product of the standard. If the value is +1, a perfect linear relationship between the variables exists. Contrary, if it is negative, there will be an inverse relationship. One variable decreases meanwhile the other increases. Finally, if the coefficient value is 0, it will indicate that there is no linear relationship between the variables. Pearson Correlation Coefficient is calculated by Equation 1.

$$P_{xy} = \begin{cases} 0 & \forall x_i, y_i < 75 \\ \frac{n \sum x_i y_i - \sum x_i \sum y_i}{\sqrt{n \sum x_i^2 - (\sum x_i)^2} \sqrt{n \sum y_i^2 - (\sum y_i)^2}} & \forall x_i, y_i \geq 75 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Where x_i and y_i are values of the raster maps to be compared, ρ_{xy} is the Pearson Correlation Coefficient, and n is the number of values analyzed.

d) Error analysis

Errors are inevitable in any analysis. Then, measured values are equally important to error estimation. There are some ways to calculate the error of a data set. In this case, the computation of the absolute error on the obtained raster is carried out by MCDM methods. It can be read as matrices according to equation (2). Then, it is part of the obtained raster through the MCDM methods. A raster is a set of cells or pixels that can be read as an array in the following way.

$$Raster = A_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & \dots & a_{1j} \\ \vdots & & \vdots \\ a_{i1} & \dots & a_{ij} \end{bmatrix} \quad \forall i, j \in \mathbb{Z} \quad (2)$$

A_{ij} : It is a tensor that contains all the values (a_{ij}) resulting from the MCDM. In this study is defined as the raster maps average (P_{ij}), as is calculated according to equation (3).

$$P_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{A_{ij}^k}{N} \quad \forall i, j \in \mathbb{Z} \quad (3)$$

Where k is the MCDM method which is operated pixel by pixel to obtain the average tensor. Then, the absolute error is calculated in equation (4), replacing equation (3).

$$E_{ij}^{(k)} = \left| P_{ij} - A_{ij}^{(k)} \right| \quad (4)$$

In order to make a comparison by method, a mean value is defined for all the absolute errors estimated by equation (4) and calculated in equation (5).

$$E^{(k)} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{N_i} \sum_{j=1}^{N_j} E_{ij}^{(k)}}{N_i N_j} \quad (5)$$

Next, the error for each method is computed by equation (6):

$$E^{(k)} = \frac{1}{N_i N_j} \sum_{i=1}^{N_i} \sum_{j=1}^{N_j} E_{ij}^{(k)} \quad \Rightarrow E_{ij} < 200 \quad (6)$$

Where:

N_i : Raster rows size

N_j : Raster columns size

The rating scale of each resulting map is from 0 to 100. The values that are outside the mask were defined as negative numbers, the same ones that do not enter in the error analysis.

3. RESULTS

Nine factors are used: global radiation, temperature, wind, electrical substation's location, electric transmission lines location, urban areas, road network, slopes, and vegetation cover as well as land usage. Each factor is weighted according to the AHP method, which is illustrated in Figure 10. These are the input data to develop the MCDM methods, such as ARAS, OCRA, PSI, SMART, Weighted Superposition, TOPSIS, and VIKOR following their respective mathematical principles. In Figure 10, the results of each MCDM method can be seen. Here, the similarities between MCDM methods (according to the graphic scale with which they are represented) are depicted and they confirm the achieved results. The correlation analysis among MCDM methods and error analysis are accomplished to determine the best locations.

Figure 11: Different MCDM assessment methods

The application of MCDM methods is carried out using R programming software. For the analysis, weights of the nine defined factors are considered, and a rating scale from 0 to 100 is applied for the standardization of information. The lowest values belong to unfit

areas, while the highest represent the suitable areas for the implementation of plants. Figure 11 shows the obtained results for seven of the MCDM methods applied. Each one of them is plotted with the same graphical scale to compare their results.

These results can be analyzed by decomposing proportionally the assessment scale to indicate a degree of soil adequacy and reduce possible risks. This is a fundamental point in pre-feasibility and feasibility studies. In this sense, the results are analyzed according to the values of pixels' groups where a valuation less than 25 represents unfit areas, a valuation from 25 to 50 represents a marginal aptitude, values from 50 to 75 moderate fitness, and amounts greater than 75 represent the most suitable sites for building locations. Also, a graphic scale of assessment appears in Figure 12.

In order to compare the suitability of lands from MCDM results, Pearson Correlation is used. The Pearson coefficient allows evaluating the similarities among all pixels of each resulting raster and providing high correlations among some methods whose r-squares are over 0.9, seeing Figure 13. Among the high obtained correlations, OCRA and superposition weighted have an r^2 value equal to 1, whereas OCRA and VIKOR values are equal to 0.94. Additionally, weighted superposition and VIKOR values are 0.94, and finally r-square between TOPSIS and VIKOR is 0.93. It is necessary to analyze the Pearson coefficient only for values higher than 75 because they correspond to sites with the greatest aptitude, Figure 13.

In a new analysis, OCRA and weighted superposition obtain a r^2 value equal to 0.98, while OCRA and VIKOR are equal to 0.95. Contrary, SMART, and TOPSIS achieve values around 0.95, and finally the weighted superposition and VIKOR equal to 0.95. Correlation values change and the relation between TOPSIS and VIKOR decrease from 0.93 to 0.23, see Figure 13. Then, correlation allows identifying similarities that each raster in accordance with its number of valued pixels.

Correlation between MCDM methods allows selecting the best results. The analysis of errors lies on obtaining an average raster among the seven methods, and then applying equation 8 to discard the method. The selected methods are which have an error up to 5%, see Table 9:

Figure 12: Correlation analysis between MCDM methods.

Figure 13: Pearson coefficient with a threshold of 75 (suitable areas)

Table 9: Errors between MCDM methods

1. The average error among the MCDM methods. The SMART method generates the highest errors.

Error	Method
35.160	ARAS
9.392	OCRA
9.674	PSI
43.750	SMART
9.174	WEIGHTED SUPERPOSITION
20.785	TOPSIS
7.791	VIKOR

2. SMART is discarded, and the method is run again. It is observed that TOPSIS is the next method with the highest error value.

Error	Method
27.869	ARAS
3.141	OCRA
8.833	PSI
3.185	WEIGHTED SUPERPOSITION
28.041	TOPSIS
4.122	VIKOR

3. TOPSIS is discarded, and it is observed that ARAS is the next method with the highest error.

Error	Method
22.263	ARAS
3.804	OCRA
10.077	PSI
4.005	WEIGHTED SUPERPOSITION
6.735	VIKOR

4. Discarded ARAS, the method is running again. It is noted that PSI is the next method with the highest error over 5%.

Error	Method
2.113	OCRA
7.637	PSI
2.159	WEIGHTED SUPERPOSITION
4.888	VIKOR

5. ARAS is discarded and the MCDM methods are running again.

Error	Method
1.690	OCRA
1.455	WEIGHTED SUPERPOSITION
2.984	VIKOR

It is noted that the average error among the OCRA, weighted superposition, and VIKOR methods are the best results. They present an absolute error less than 5%. Nevertheless, the first analysis based on absolute errors and Pearson coefficient confirms that the weighted superposition and OCRA methods have the highest correlation. It indicates that these methods give equal results. Therefore, they are being evaluated twice, and the next

step is to perform the same analysis without the weighted superposition method to make a decision. The analysis is shown in Table 10.

In addition, the final average between OCRA and VIKOR is adjusted to a scale from 1 to 100 for the whole territory. Other averages do not show assessed values in the defined total scale, the pixels do not coincide with their geographical position and valuation.

Table 10: Errors among MCDM methods without weighted overlap

1. The average error among the six MCDM methods. The SMART method generates the highest errors.

Error	Method
36.664	ARAS
10.913	OCRA
10.363	PSI
42.246	SMART
19.280	TOPSIS
9.031	VIKOR

2. SMART is discarded, and the method is executed again. Here, it is noted that ARAS is the next method with the highest error.

Error	Method
28.215	ARAS
3.743	OCRA
8.859	PSI
27.693	TOPSIS
4.377	VIKOR

3. ARAS is discarded, and it is noted that TOPSIS is the next method with the highest error.

Error	Method
9.369	OCRA
9.435	PSI
20.838	TOPSIS
6.989	VIKOR

4. TOPSIS is discarded and the MCDM methods are running again. It is observed that PSI is the next method with the highest error above 5%.

Error	Method
2.761	OCRA
7.070	PSI
5.289	VIKOR

According to the second error analysis, the best result is between OCRA and VIKOR methods with an error less than 5% and a correlation of 0.94%. Therefore, the best selection of places is between the averages of these two methods, see Table 10. Then, restricted areas are excluded and possible areas for solar farms are selected how it shows in Figure 14.

Figure 14: MCE Result Map.

Figure 14 indicates that the final average raster between the OCRA and VIKOR methods is classified according to certain rating ranges. In this way, the restricted areas adopt a zero value, and they are classified as not suitable. They represent 79% of Ecuadorian territory with an area of 197533.96 km². On the other hand, the areas that surpass the 95% aptitude are in the Andean region, and they represent 3312 km² that corresponds to 1.3% of the whole Ecuadorian territory. These areas are selected as suitable, which are

concentrated in the next provinces: Loja, Pichincha, Santo Domingo de los Tsáchilas, and Cotopaxi. Nonetheless, El Oro province located in the Coastal region also presents a great suitability for the geolocation of solar farms. Table 11 summarizes these results.

Table 11: MCE results from classification by area.

Id	MCE classification	Definition	MCE area [Km ²]	%
0	0	Unfit	197533.96	79.337
1	1 to 25	Unfit	0.52	0.000
2	26 to 50	Marginal	1298.6	0.522
3	50 to 75	Moderate	17101.88	6.869
4	75 to 80	Suitable	5831	2.342
5	80 to 85	Suitable	8006.84	3.216
6	85 to 90	Suitable	10521.28	4.226
7	90 to 95	Suitable	5375.52	2.159
8	95 to 100	Suitable	3312.6	1.330
Total area of Ecuador			248982.2	100%

The Andean region, places with the greatest aptitude for the construction of photovoltaic solar farms have 95% aptitude (represented by red color). These locations are mostly located in Loja (south of Ecuador), followed by Santo Domingo, Pichincha, Cotopaxi, and Imbabura which are provinces located in the northern center of the country. Finally, less suitable areas with a valuation less than 50% (represented with green color) are in the provinces of Chimborazo and Azuay (Figure 15).

In addition, in the Coastal area, it is prominent the suitability for solar farms in El Oro (south of the country). Although provinces such as Manabí, Guayas and Los Ríos are not as suitable as El Oro, they present a MCE classification higher than 75 % which makes them suitable areas for solar farm installations. Conversely, a major part of Esmeraldas is not recommended for the abovementioned purpose as can be seen in Figure 15.

Furthermore, in the Amazon region, it has been identified that the northwestern zone of this region is suitable for solar energy collection. To be specific, the western areas of Napo, Sucumbíos, Orellana, and Pastaza have an aptitude higher than 75%. On the other hand, Zamora Chinchipe, the eastern zone of Pastaza, and the southern area of Morona Santiago have been established as not suitable for this purpose.

Figure 15: Geolocation of places for solar farm installing in the continental area of Ecuador

4. DISCUSSION

This research show that some areas of Ecuador have a good potential to install photovoltaic plants for electric generation. Solar farms could be connected to the Ecuadorian electrical system or directly supply electricity to nearby populations. The location of solar farms corresponds to a combination of GIS and MCDM methods. Once results are obtained and correlation analysis performed among the proposed methods, it is verified that the average between two MCDM methods gives the best results. Related with these results, the solution is evaluated by means of error analysis, and it is resolved that the average between OCRA and VIKOR is the best solution for selecting proper locations. Results have a high rate of acceptance in the implementation of solar farms under the Ecuadorian energy regulation which is necessary to generate at least 1 MW to be considered as a solar farm. According to this background information, the EURO-SOLAR project is currently underway. It promotes the development of renewable energy focused on improving the quality of life for some populations. Under the frame of this project, Ecuadorian Coast (Guayas, Esmeraldas) and Jungle region (Sucumbios, Orellana, Napo, Pastaza, and Morona Santiago) provinces were benefited, meanwhile areas with suitable potential for the installation of solar farms were excluded, as concluded in this study. To be specific, the profitability of provinces such as Loja, El Oro, Pichincha, Santo Domingo de los Tsáchilas, Cotopaxi, and Imbabura have not been taken advantage in this project. Therefore, this research is expected to become a decision-making tool, and the main goal is to encourage the use of renewable energies for providing basic services to

populations in need in the above-mentioned areas that are apt and convenient for solar energy aims.

In case of Ecuador, Cevallos-Sierra and Ramos-Martín [9] developed a GIS study of the areas with higher potential for the development of renewable energy projects (REP). In case of Geolocation of photovoltaic farms using GIS with MCDM methods in the continental territory of Ecuador, instead of carrying out multi-objective work with GIS, it has been used GIS and MCDM methods. In this research, nine factors are used to carry out the MCDM analysis. AHP method is the most suitable to determine the weights for the considered factors. Using this information, the method is used to select the best location for photovoltaic solar energy generation projects. This methodology is corroborated in the research of San Cristobal [47] or Uyan for the Karapinar region (Konya / Turkey) [28]. In the weighting process, it is defined that the climatic hierarchical group has a weight of 40 % in comparison with the socioeconomic group that has 35 % and the environmental 25 %. The climatic is the most important group since it defines the potential electricity generation of a solar farm, as are show in the research [17-59]. Then, socioeconomic, and environmental groups show that the feasibility in this type of project is closely linked to the type of orography infrastructure near the selected areas. The wind farm in Villonaco (south of Ecuador), which was built at high altitudes is a clear example. Once the criteria are organized hierarchically and the values are consistent, the same process is repeated with the seven MCDM methods such as ARAS, OCRA, PSI, SMART, weighted superposition, TOPSIS, and VIKOR. The combination of GIS and MCDM methods are the fundamental support for the development of this research as was demonstrated by Watson and Hudson in [48] for the asses the suitability solar farms (at a regional scale).

In case Cevallos-Sierra and Ramos-Martín research's [9] of Ecuador, their results show that solar PV is the technology with most suitable areas in the country and demonstrate particularly large potential in Loja and Galápagos Islands. In addition, the provinces of El Oro, Imbabura, Pichincha, and Sto. Domingo de los Tsáchilas showed fitting features for solar PV applications. This study confirms the results obtained by [4]. Nevertheless, it was found that Cotopaxi, Manabí, Guayas, Los Ríos, the western areas of Napo, Sucumbíos, Orellana, and Pastaza have also suitable characteristics for the use of solar farms. Specifically, this research used GIS tools to identify the locations, with the greatest potential, for the development of medium-scale and largescale solar, power plants. In the case of Geolocation of photovoltaic farms using GIS with MCDM methods, instead of carrying results for develop medium-scale and largescale solar, power plants, the research is focus on Ecuadorian energy regulation. Result maps have been obtained which provide suitable and not suitable areas for the construction of projects. To sum up, El Oro, Loja and some provinces in the center north of the country such as Pichincha, Santo Domingo de Los Tsáchilas, Cotopaxi, and Imbabura are the most adequate because of their great global solar radiation, wind speed, and temperature for cooling solar panels. In contrast, provinces such as Esmeraldas (Coastal region), Azuay (Andes region), and Zamora Chinchipe (Amazonian region) are the less suitable for the installation of solar farms.

Moreover, to achieve these results, an analysis of seven MCDM methods results was performed using the Pearson correlation coefficient, followed by absolute error analysis. By Pearson, it is demonstrated that there are methods with a high correlation between them. It is explained by the fact that they have many pixels with similar values, but these values are independent of geographical location. This is a plus to the multi-objective GIS analysis of Cevallos-Sierra and Ramos-Martín research's [9]

In case of Ecuador Cevallos-Sierra and Ramos-Martín [9] initially recommends geographic locations for the installation of measuring towers of solar and wind resources, in order to obtain more detailed infriected areas adopted a zero value and are classified as unfit for this research. Of the selected areas for solar farm location, those that surpass 95 % aptitude. These areas, most in the Andean region, represent 3312 km², and corresponds to 1.3 % of the country. Although the resolution is low, areas are taken into account where studies can be carried out to introduce solar farms under the Ecuadorian energy regulation.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This research develops the geolocation of photovoltaic farms using GIS with MCDM methods under the Ecuadorian energy regulation in the continental territory of this country. The combination of GIS and MCDM methods are the fundamental support for the development of this research. Each one confirmed by its own factors. In addition, these components, the restrictive criteria or limitations to achieve the proposed objective were considered. It is expected that the results have a high rate of acceptance in the implementation of solar farms under the Ecuadorian energy regulation which is necessary to generate at least 1 MW to be considered as a solar farm.

The AHP methodology is used for Weighting the different factors. It allows assessing the criteria according to the bibliography and the experience of the authors. In this paper, a combination of the two options is carried out, working directly with personnel from the Instituto Nacional de Eficiencia Energética y Energías Renovables (INER). They are experts in the matter at the international level. In addition, seven MCDM methods such as ARAS, OCRA, PSI, SMART, weighted superposition, TOPSIS, and VIKOR are applied.

Loja, El Oro and some provinces in the center north of the country such as Pichincha, Santo Domingo de Los Tsáchilas, and Cotopaxi are the most adequate because of their great global solar radiation, wind speed, and temperature for cooling solar panels. In contrast, provinces of Esmeraldas, Cañar, Azuay, and Zamora Chinchipe with values less than 50%, are the locations with the lowest potential for the installation of solar farms. By considering the total area of continental Ecuador, areas with aptitude values less than 75% represent 86.7% of the whole country.

In order to give focus, the correlation of the achieved results for each method was verified by means of a Pearson evaluation considering a limit over 75 % proficiency. This showed a change of values according to the relationship among methods. A clear example is the

correlation between TOPSIS and VIKOR, which compares that all their pixels have a correlation of 0.9. In the same way, this comparison analyzes that a threshold equals 75% corresponds to a correlation of 0.2%.

In the case of relocating solar farms in the Coast and Amazon regions of Ecuador, it was considered restrictions of coverage. In particular, it was considered the National System of Protected Areas, urban areas, and water areas. Also, for the Coast region, it was considered mangrove cover and flood zones.

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